

STOCHASTIC VIRTUAL TESTS FOR FIBER COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Composites

ABSTRACT

Virtual tests combine experiments and theory to address physical, mathematical, and engineering aspects of material definition and failure prediction. The main research steps are: high resolution three-dimensional (3D) imaging of the microstructure, statistical characterization of the microstructure, formulation of a probabilistic generator for creating virtual specimens that replicate the measured statistics, creation of a computational model for a virtual specimen that allows general representation of discrete damage events, calibration of the model using high temperature tests, simulation of failure, and model validation. Key new experiments include digital surface image correlation and μm -resolution 3D imaging of the microstructure and evolving damage, both executed at temperatures exceeding 1500°C. Conceptual advances include using both geometry and topology to characterize stochastic microstructures. Computational methods include new probabilistic algorithms for generating stochastic virtual specimens and a new Augmented Finite Element Method (A-FEM) that yields extreme efficiency in dealing with arbitrary cracking in such heterogeneous materials. The challenge of predicting the probability of an extreme failure event for a given stochastic microstructure in a computationally tractable manner, while retaining necessary physical details in models, is discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

In a common paradigm based on Monte Carlo methods, the virtual test is built by the following steps (e.g., [1-8]).

1. The microstructure of the real material is measured and characterized in all the details that are likely to influence predicted material behaviour.
2. The measured microstructural characteristics, being stochastic, are fitted by distribution functions.

3. An ensemble of virtual specimens is generated by the Monte Carlo method, each of which, while being distinct from any real specimen, nevertheless possesses a microstructure with the same statistics as those measured on the real specimens.
4. The material properties associated with the virtual specimen, including, for example, the fracture laws that govern crack initiation and propagation, are calibrated by real tests.
5. Damage evolution is simulated for each virtual specimen in the ensemble, taking explicit account of the influence of the particular local microstructure present in any region of the specimen on the damage events that are occurring in that region.
6. The virtual test is validated by comparing the statistics of failure predicted for the ensemble of virtual specimens against those from tests on real specimens

The general approach to stochastic virtual tests reviewed in this paper consists of determining defects as geometrical variances in the material and then predicting their effect on properties (i.e., their strength as defects) by high-fidelity simulations of failure [9]. For pragmatic reasons, this method is embedded in a top-down strategy [10]: the defects are sought first at the largest scale (where geometrical variance is easiest to measure) and then at progressively finer scales. In due course, with perfect experiments, the strategy could in principle be pursued down through all scales to the atomic. However, in reality at any time in the history of developing virtual tests, the geometry cannot be measured exhaustively at scales beneath some threshold. Yet evidence implies indisputably that defects at finer scales do exist, even if they are as yet invisible, and govern some aspects of failure.

Figure 1. A pipeline approach to assembling a cross-disciplinary virtual test system.

2 VIRTUAL TESTS FOR HIGH-TEMPERATURE CONTINUOUS FIBER COMPOSITES

Virtual tests are of special value for high temperature materials, e.g., the current generation of integral textile ceramic matrix composites [11-13], with potential use temperatures ranging up to 1500°C [14-16]. Strong continuous fiber bundles (scale 0.1–1mm) are woven in custom-designed 3-D patterns, with individual bundles oriented to follow the primary load paths in a component to maximize its strength, and interlocked with one another to prevent catastrophic separation when damaged. Larger interstices between the fiber bundles may be partially filled with randomly-oriented fine reinforcing rods (scale: 1 – 10 μm), inhibiting local cracking

under thermal shock. Coatings applied to individual fibers (scale: 0.1 – 1 μm) inhibit chemical reactions and ensure that the interfaces between the fibers and the matrix remain weak, allowing ductile response through matrix cracking and frictional pullout of crack-bridging fibers. The remaining space between coated fibers, fiber bundles, and reinforcing rods is filled with a ceramic-matrix material, which itself may be a hybrid containing, for example, graphitic sheets that inhibit oxygen ingress (scale: 1–100nm) [17]. Thus, like many natural materials, these new ceramic composites achieve robustness through complexity: their hierarchical, hybrid microstructure impedes the growth of local damage and prevents the large fatal cracks that are characteristic of brittle materials.

While mechanisms of failure in composites that act at room temperature can be determined quite readily either by modern 3D imaging or by destructive sectioning following interruption of tests, mechanisms acting at high temperatures are much more difficult to probe. Even surface observations tend to be obscured by radiation if observed *in situ*, while observations at room temperature following test interruption will be influenced to an unknown degree by the thermo-mechanical effects of cooling from the test temperature. The virtual test offers the possibility of probing details of damage mechanisms for different temperature and loading histories using simulations coupled to relatively simple surface observations on real specimens. Nevertheless, advancing test methods applicable to high temperatures remains critical: the proven fidelity of a virtual test can never exceed the ability to identify the mechanisms that must be modeled by direct experimentation.

In the case of virtual tests for continuous-fiber composites, including composites reinforced by laminated unidirectional fiber plies and textile preforms, the high resolution now available in X-ray CT imaging systems is yielding details of the stochastic variability of plies and fiber tows, and even the spatial distribution of individual fibers. Certain characteristics of textile geometry and tow deformation have been measured [18-20], as well as porosity [21] and its changes during processing steps [21, 22]. The same technique is now yielding 3D images of damage captured *in situ* under load at very high temperatures, which is key to informing simulations of damage evolution [23].

These and other studies have also addressed achieving feature definition in ceramic composites [24], which is often made difficult by low x-ray absorption contrast between the constituent materials. In recent work, fiber tows are made to stand out by imaging composites with partially formed matrices [25].

The importance of geometrical defects in fibrous composites is already well understood from decades of research on polymer and ceramic composites: variability in fiber positioning is a principal source of scatter in composite performance. In polymer composites, for example, strength in monotonic compression and fatigue life in compression-compression fatigue are both influenced by local misalignments in fiber bundles, which lead to kink band instabilities [26-31]. Kink bands have not been observed in ceramic composites, but tow straightening occurs under tension, implying local damage within tows that is driven by local shear stresses, which will correlate with the degree of tow misalignment. In both polymer and brittle matrix composites, fracture of a fiber ply or tow loaded in tension perpendicular to the fiber direction tends to initiate at and propagate through locations where the fiber spacing is unusually small [32] and oblique fiber bridging across transverse cracks correlates with fiber meandering [33]. The importance of avoiding fiber misalignments and wrinkles and other fiber deployment defects has become well recognized by those involved in modelling and controlling the textile forming process [34].

3 RECENT ADVANCES

Recent advances towards a functional virtual test system include the following.

- (i) Simple standard sets of statistical metrics quantify the geometrical variances in the fiber reinforcement that are likely to influence failure [25, 35-38]. At the tow scale, variance refers to the position and shapes of tows. At the fiber scale, both topological and Euclidean metrics are required, the former to describe the meanderings and entanglements of fibers within a tow, the latter to describe local packing densities, etc. [33]. Analytical methods have been developed to deduce metrics from experimental images acquired by μ CT for single tows or unit-cell sized specimens, and by digital image analysis for sub-component-sized specimens [37].
- (ii) At the unit-cell scale and the much larger scale of sub-components, algorithms have been invented for rapidly generating ensembles of stochastic virtual specimens in which the variances of tow locations and shapes match the statistical metrics determined for real specimens [35, 36]. Generating virtual specimens at the fiber scale with variance matching measured topological and Euclidean metrics remains a current research topic.
- (iii) New experimental systems have been developed to observe and measure damage evolution in ceramic composites at very high temperatures. A digital image correlation system observes surface damage with optical resolution using standard coupons at temperatures above 1500°C, while a μ CT test rig determines damage with sub-micron resolution in 3D in miniature coupon specimens at temperatures above 1700°C [23, 39].
- (iv) Representative of widespread activity in developing fast simulation methods with generalized capability, a reformulation of the Augmented Finite Element Method (A-FEM) [40] has achieved high-fidelity simulation of multiple crack systems in arbitrarily heterogeneous materials [41]. The A-FEM correctly describes the mechanics of crack bifurcation and coalescence in the presence of nonlinear fracture mechanisms acting along crack process zones [42, 43]. The reformulation has also achieved very high speeds relative to prior standards in multi-crack simulations. Speed is vital when analyzing large ensembles of stochastic virtual specimens, as required to relate failure distributions to variance in microstructure.
- (v) In a display of the potential of 3D μ CT imaging as a probe of local material behaviour, the friction stress acting at the fiber/matrix interface, which controls the question of whether matrix cracking across a fiber tow occurs in a brittle or ductile manner, has been calibrated at both room temperature and 1650°C for a representative material using analysis of μ CT fracture tests [23].
- (vi) High-fidelity simulations have themselves been used to deduce cohesive fracture law parameters from complex test data, illustrating how traditional standard test methods can be complemented by tests that deal with events occurring at small scales inside a heterogeneous material [42]. Thus calibrated, the simulations correctly predict complex cracking systems in an angle interlock weave and in laminated T-stiffener specimens [9]. The fidelity with which the details of crack evolution can be reproduced matches that previously demonstrated for polymer tape laminate composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

While such successes encourage the ambition to develop virtual tests, a number of fundamental challenges remain ahead.

As simulations seek to probe the influence of stochastic microstructure at the scale of the individual fiber ($\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$), or at the even finer scale of random hybrid nanostructures ($\sim 1 - 100 \text{ nm}$), the complexity of a complete material description becomes formidable. Furthermore, because the question of the order in which failure events will occur at different locations is increasingly finely balanced as the complexity of the material increases, the likelihood arises that aspects of simulations (in correspondence with nature) will exhibit chaotic character. Whether the influence of increasing complexity on properties can be analyzed by simply pushing simulations of multiple discrete damage events to larger and larger problems (smaller and smaller scales) is doubtful; new methods may be required to cover multiple scales without compromising fidelity.

To complete the association of performance with microstructural variance, whether for material design or for material certification, a virtual test must be executed for a statistically significant number of instantiations of the microstructure. Solving typical predictive cases in a reasonable time poses the challenging target of 1 sec as the time, to order of magnitude, for a single simulation when $10^4 - 10^6$ simulations are needed in Monte Carlo strategies. Alternative probabilistic models, in which one tracks the evolution in time of probability density functions for damage rather than the damage itself, offer speed but require new formulations to maintain fidelity. The probabilistic models must include the essential microstructural factors in laws governing the density evolution or else lose fidelity.

Ongoing extensions of the virtual test system for ceramic composites include the incorporation of environmental and other rate effects, especially oxidation at high temperature and creep.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the US AFOSR (Dr. Ali Sayir) and NASA (Dr. Anthony Calomino) under the National Hypersonics Science Center for Materials and Structures (AFOSR Contract No. FA9550-09-1-0477).

REFERENCES

1. Cox, B.N. and Q.D. Yang, *In quest of virtual tests for structural composites*. Science, 2006. **314**: p. 1102-1107.
2. Cox, B.N. and Q.D. Yang. *Virtual Tests of Laminated Composites - Adding the Sublaminar Scale*. in *ECCOMAS Conference on Composites*. 2009. London, UK: ECCOMAS.
3. Llorca, J. and B.N. Cox, eds. *Virtual fracture testing of composite materials and structures, Proceedings from the World Congress on Computational Mechanics*. International Journal of Fracture, ed. K. Ravi-Chandar. Vol. 158. 2010.
4. Groeber, M., et al., *A framework for automated analysis and simulation of 3D polycrystalline microstructures. Part 2: Synthetic structure generation*. Acta Materialia, 2008. **56**: p. 1274-1287.
5. Pollock, T.M., et al., *Integrated computational materials engineering: A transformational discipline for improved competitiveness and national security*. 2008, National Research Council of the National Academies: Washington, D.C.
6. . in *1st World Congress on Integrated Computational Materials Engineering (ICME)*. 2011. Seven Springs, PA: Wiley Online.
7. Cox, B.N., *Inductions from Monte Carlo simulations of small fatigue cracks*. Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 1989. **33**: p. 655-670.

8. Cox, B.N. and W.L. Morris, *Monte Carlo simulations of the growth of small fatigue cracks*. Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 1988. **31**: p. 591-610.
9. Cox, B.N., et al., *Stochastic Virtual Tests for High-Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composites*. Annual Review of Materials Research, 2014(0).
10. Hutchinson, J.W. and A.G. Evans, *Mechanics of Materials: Top-Down Approaches to Fracture*. Acta Materialia, 2000. **48**: p. 125-135.
11. Ko, F.K., *Preform Fiber Architecture for Ceramic-Matrix Composites*. Ceramic Bulletin, 1989. **68**(2): p. 401-414.
12. Marshall, D.B. and B.N. Cox, *Integral textile ceramic structures*. Annual Review of Materials Research, 2008. **38**: p. 425-443.
13. Mouritz, A.P., et al., *Review of applications for advanced three-dimensional fibre textile composites*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 1999. **30**(12): p. 1445-1461.
14. Schmidt, S., et al., *Ceramic matrix composites: A challenge in space-propulsion technology applications*. International Journal of Applied Ceramic Technology, 2005. **2**(2): p. 85-96.
15. Morscher, G.N. and V.V. Pujar, *Design Guidelines for In-Plane Mechanical Properties of SiC Fiber-Reinforced Melt-Infiltrated SiC Composites*. International Journal of Applied Ceramic Technology, 2009. **6**(2): p. 151-163.
16. Zhao, J.C. and J.H. Westbrook, *Ultrahigh-temperature materials for jet engines*. Mrs Bulletin, 2003. **28**(9): p. 622-630.
17. Raj, R., A. Scarmi, and G.D. Soraru, *The role of carbon in unexpected visco(an)elastic behavior of amorphous silicon oxycarbide above 1273K*. Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids, 2005. **351**(27-29): p. 2238-43.
18. Badel, P., et al., *Simulation and tomography analysis of textile composite reinforcement deformation at the mesoscopic scale*. Composites Science and Technology, 2008. **68**: p. 2433-2440.
19. Desplentere, F., et al., *Micro-CT characterization of variability in 3D textile architecture*. Composite Science and Technology, 2005. **65**: p. 1920-1930.
20. Mahadik, Y., K.A. Robson Brown, and S.R. Hallett, *Characterisation of 3D woven composite internal architecture and effect of compaction*. Composites, Part A, 2010. **41**: p. 872-880.
21. Lee, S.-B., et al., *Pore geometry in woven fiber structures: 0/90 plain-weave cloth layup preform*. Journal of Materials Research, 1998. **13**(5): p. 1209-1217.
22. Kinney, J.H., et al., *X-ray tomographic study of chemical vapor infiltration processing of ceramic composites*. Science, 1993. **260**: p. 789-792.
23. Bale, H.A., et al., *Real-Time Quantitative Imaging of Failure Events in Ultrahigh-Temperature Materials under Load at Unprecedented Temperatures above 1700°C*. Nature Materials, 2013. **12**(1): p. 40-46.
24. Coindreau, O., G. Vignoles, and P. Cloetens, *Direct 3D microscale imaging of carbon-carbon composites with computed holotomography*. Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research B, 2003. **200**: p. 308-314.
25. Bale, H., et al., *Characterizing Three-Dimensional Textile Ceramic Composites using Synchrotron X-Ray Micro-Computed-Tomography*. Journal of the American Ceramic Society, 2011. **95**(1): p. 392-402.
26. Argon, A.S., *Fracture of composites*. Treatise of Materials Sciences and Technology. Vol. 1. 1972, New York: Academic Press.
27. Budiansky, B., *Micromechanics*. Composite Structures, 1983. **16**(1): p. 3-12.

28. Cox, B.N., et al., *Mechanisms of compressive failure in 3D composites*. Acta Metallurgica et Materialia, 1992. **40**: p. 3285-3298.
29. Fleck, N.A. and B. Budiansky, *Compressive failure of fibre composites due to microbuckling*, in *Inelastic Deformation of Composite Materials*, G.J. Dvorak, Editor. 1991, Springer-Verlag: New York. p. 235-274.
30. Fleck, N.A. and J.Y. Shu, *Microbuckle initiation in fibre composites: a finite element study*. Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, 1995. **43**(12): p. 1887-1918.
31. Dadkhah, M.S., et al., *Simple models for triaxially braided composites*. Composites, 1995. **26**: p. 91-102.
32. Marshall, D.B., et al., *Transverse strengths and failure mechanisms in Ti3Al matrix composites*. Acta Metallurgica et Materialia, 1994. **42**: p. 2657-2673.
33. Fast, T., et al., *Topological and Euclidean metrics reveal spatially non-uniform structure in the entanglement of stochastic fiber bundles*. Journal of Materials Science, 2014. DOI [10.1007/s10853-014-8766-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-014-8766-2).
34. Gereke, T., et al., *Experimental and computational composite textile reinforcement forming: A review*. Composite Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2013. **46**: p. 1-10.
35. Blacklock, M., et al., *Generating virtual textile composite specimens using statistical data from micro-computed tomography: 1D tow representations for the Binary Model*. Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, 2012. **60**: p. 451-470.
36. Rinaldi, R., et al., *Generating virtual textile composite specimens using statistical data from micro-computed tomography: 3D tow representations*. Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, 2012. **60**(8): p. 1561-1581.
37. Rossol, M.N., et al., *Characterizing in-plane geometrical variability in textile ceramic composites*. Journal of the American Ceramic Society, 2015. **98**(1): p. 205-213.
38. Vanaerschot, A., et al., *Stochastic multi-scale modelling of textile composites based on internal geometry variability*. Computers & Structures, 2013. **122**: p. 55-64.
39. Shaw, J.H., et al., *Towards a Virtual Test for C/SiC Textile Composites: Calibration of Thermoelastic Tow Properties*. Journal of the American Ceramic Society, 2013. **submitted**.
40. Ling, D., Q. Yang, and B.N. Cox, *An augmented finite element method for modeling arbitrary discontinuities in composite materials*. International Journal of Fracture, 2009. **156**: p. 53-73.
41. Liu, W., et al., *An accurate and efficient augmented finite element method for arbitrary crack interactions*. Journal of Applied Mechanics, 2013. **80**(4): p. 041033.
42. Fang, X.J., et al., *High-fidelity simulations of multiple fracture processes in laminated composites in tension*. Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, 2011. **59**: p. 1355-1373.
43. Yang, Q., et al., *On crack initiation in notched, cross-plyed polymer matrix composites*. Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, 2015. **78**: p. 314-332.